

COST-EFFECTIVE SYNTHESIS OF COPPER/DIAMOND COMPOSITE WITH ACCEPTABLE THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Copper/diamond composites have great potential to lead the next generation of heat-sink materials, with a high thermal conductivity and thermal expansion coefficient that is tunable to match with that of commercial chip materials, in the range of $4-6 \times 10^{-6}/K$. However, their potentially high thermal conductivity is strongly dependent on the quality of the copper/diamond interface, which is disrupted by the poor wettability of copper and diamond. In this paper, Cu-x wt%Ti- (55-65)vol%Dia composites (x=1, 1.5, 3 and 4.5) were fabricated by induction sintering and forging from powder preform. TiC interface layer is formed between the copper and the diamond in the fabricated composites and the coverage of the diamond particle by TiC interface layer is increased with increasing the titanium addition. When titanium content is over 3wt% in the copper alloy, Cu₄Ti is inclined to form, which leads to the TiC interface layer spall from the diamond surface. Effective TiC interface layer is formed in the Cu-1.5wt% Ti-55vol%Dia composite, and the interface covers most of the diamond particle surfaces, leading to the composite has acceptable thermal conductivity (388W/m·K) that almost double the value of current best practice of heat sink materials for high-power electronics, AlN. It is feasible and cost-effective to use the combination techniques of induction heating and forging to produce copper/diamond composite with acceptable thermal conductivity, meeting the application requirement of future high-power electronic device.

1 INTRODUCTION

The technical capabilities of modern electronic devices increasingly demand higher frequencies and more power^[1-3]. However, the power and longevity of electronic chips used in terahertz, high-thermal-density/ultra-high-frequency and high-power electronics are strongly dependent on thermophysical properties of the heat sink^[2], which requires high thermal conductivity and similar thermal expansion to that of chip materials (Si, InP, GaAs).

Diamond and other existing heat-sink materials (e.g. AlN, Al₂O₃, Cu-W) have mismatched thermal expansion coefficients to that of chip materials and/or insufficient thermal conductivity ($<200W/(m \cdot K)$)^[4]. Thus, they cannot rapidly remove all the heat generated by high-power electronic devices, causing stress on the chip. Materials that have both high thermal conductivity and similar thermal expansion rates to commercial chip materials are therefore in high demand for use as heat sinks in these applications.

Copper/diamond composite materials have great potential to achieve the required heat-sink properties. However, the thermal conductivity of copper/diamond composites is dependent on the quality of the copper/diamond interface^[1,5,6], and sintering copper/diamond composites is challenging due to the poor wettability between copper and diamond^[4,6-10]. To improve the wettability, minor carbide-forming elements (e.g. Ti, Cr, Zr, W, B)^[1, 11-14] have been introduced to form a carbide interfacial layer between the diamond particle and the copper matrix in the copper/diamond composites. Current manufacturing technologies, such as High Temperature and High Pressure methods^[15], Gas Pressure Infiltration^[16,17] and Spark Plasma Sintering^[18-20], require highly specialised equipment and long fabrication process, resulting in prohibitively expensive materials and impeding commercial applications.

In this paper, we explore a cost-effective route that combine induction heating and hot forging to prepare copper/diamond composites from a powder preform which is composed of artificial diamond, copper powder, and small amount of titanium addition. We investigated the effects of titanium addition and diamond volume fraction on the fabricated composite's relative density, microstructure, interface characteristics, and thermal conductivity.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The raw materials used were dendritic copper powder (99.7 wt% in purity, < 45 μm), hydride-dehydrided Ti powder (99.6 wt% in purity, < 75 μm), and MBD8 diamond (70~80 μm , supplied by Henan Huanghe Whirlwind Co., China) powder. A powder mixtures with the nominal composition of Cu-xwt%Ti-65vol%Dia (x=1, 3, 4.5) and Cu-1.5wt%Ti-55vol%Dia, respectively, were blended in a V-type blender at 60 rpm for 90 min. Then the powder mixture was pressed into $\text{\O}40$ mm compact with a thickness of about 33 mm. After that, the compact was (1) induction sintered at 1050 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1.5 min or (2) loaded in a steel can and induction heated up to 1050 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and forged into a pancake. The details of hot forging can be found in Ref.[21].

A scanning electron microscope (SEM, HITACHI, S4700) equipped with EDS (Thermo Noran, accelerating voltage is 20 kV) and TEM (Tecnai G2 F20 S-TWIN, 200KV) were used to characterise the microstructures of copper/diamond composites and nitric acid-extracted diamond particles from the composites. The phase constituents were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD, Cu K α radiation). Samples for SEM observation were etched in a nitric acid aqueous solution with the volume ratio of 1 HNO_3 : 10 H_2O , and a dual beam focused ion beam workstation system (FIB, FEI Helios NanoLabTM 600i, USA) was used to prepare TEM specimens from the fabricated composite.

The thermal conductivity (λ) was calculated using the equation $\lambda = \alpha \rho c_p$, where α is the thermal diffusivity, ρ is sample density and c_p is specific heat capacity. The thermal diffusivity was measured by a laser flash technique using a LFA 467 instrument (Netzsch, Germany) at room temperature. The cylindrical samples used had dimensions of $\text{\O}12.5$ mm \times 3 mm. The samples were grinded with abrasive papers coded as 320# and 1000# and then cleaned ultrasonically in ethanol for 5 min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the microstructure of Cu-1wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite which is induction-sintered at 1050 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1.5min, and the morphology of diamond particles extracted from the composite. Large-sized pores are visible in Fig.1a, and porous area is observed in the high magnification image (Fig.1b), showing that the copper matrix is not fully consolidated under the induction sintering condition, and this can be further confirmed by a measured relative density of 76.3% for the induction-sintered composite. In order to investigate the interface formation between the copper and the diamond, the diamond particle is extracted from the composite, and its backscattered electron image is shown in Fig.1c. Together with EDS results (Table 1), we confirm that the black particles are diamonds and the grey areas on the diamond particles are the formed interface, of which composition is composed of Ti and C. XRD analysis (Fig. 2a) exhibits that TiC peaks are indexed together with the peaks of diamond

Fig. 1 Microstructure of Cu-1wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite induction-sintered at 1050 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1.5min: (a) and (b), and the extracted diamond particles from the composite: (c)

and copper in the 1050°C-induction-sintered Cu-1wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite. Combining EDS and XRD analysis, it suggests that the formed interface in Fig. 1c is TiC. The TiC interface only covers very few diamond particles' surface (Fig. 1c), indicating that the TiC interface can be formed between the copper and diamond in the composite during induction sintering, but the amount of formed TiC is very few due to the short sintering time, so that the coverage of the diamond particle by the interface is very low. It can predict that the thermal conductivity of the induction-sintered copper/diamond composite is low due to the low relative density and ineffective interface formation between the copper and the diamond.

Table 1 Chemical composition of point position in Fig. 1

Point position	C (wt%)	Ti (wt%)
1	99.30	0.70
2	42.04	57.96

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the fabricated copper/diamond composites: (a) Cu-1wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia (Induction sintered), (b) Cu-1wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia (forged), (c) Cu-3wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia (forged), and (d) Cu-4.5wt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia (forged)

To optimise the synthesis process of copper/diamond composite for improving the relative density and forming effective interface, the induction-sintered copper/diamond composite billets are further forged. The microstructures of hot-forged Cu-xwt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia composites (x=1, 3 and 4.5) at 1050°C and the morphology of the extracted diamond particles are shown in Fig. 3. No obvious pores are observed for the forged composites (Fig. 3a and b), and the relative density of the forged composites are higher than that of the induction-sintered composite, with a measured value of 84.8% for Cu-1wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia, 87.6% for Cu-3wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia, and 86.3% for Cu-4.5wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia. Comparing to the forged Cu-1wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite, the interface between the copper and the diamond is visible in the forged Cu-3wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite, as shown in Fig. 3b and c (marked as red arrow), and an obvious interface can be seen in the high magnification image (Fig. 3d). EDS line scanning (Fig.3d inset) shows that the interface is rich in Ti and C, indicating that TiC interface layer is formed. For the extracted diamond particles (Fig.3e and f), we can clearly see

that more diamond surfaces are covered by the TiC interface layer for the forged Cu-1wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite comparing to that in the corresponding induction-sintered composite. This suggests that the pressure assisted sintering can promote TiC formation comparing to the pressureless sintering (induction sintering), which is mainly attributed to that the mass transportation accelerated by applying pressure. With increasing Ti addition to 3wt%, the coverage of diamond surface by TiC interface is slightly increased, but the coverage is still less than 50%. Further increasing titanium content to 4.5wt%, the coverage of diamond by TiC is dramatically reduced and bared diamond surfaces are visible (Fig.3g and f), this is because the formed interface spall from the diamond particle surface (Fig. 3f).

Fig. 3 Microstructures of Cu-xwt.%Ti-65vol.%Dia composites (x=1, 3 and 4.5) hot forging at 1050°C (a-d) and morphologies of the extracted diamond particles from the composites: (e and f): x=1 for (a) and (e), x= 3 for (b) – (d) and (f) , x=4.5 for (g) and (h)

The images of nitric-corroded Cu-3wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite are seen in Fig. 4. A gap is visible between the TiC interface and diamond particle (Fig. 4a and b), and it can also see that large number of flake-shaped pieces exist in the gap, with a dimension of about 3-5 μ m in diameter and <0.5 μ m in thickness. However, the composition of these flake pieces is hard to be analysed by EDS due to the signal shielding problem from the neighbouring diamond particles and TiC layer. From XRD analysis (Fig. 2d), we can see that Cu₄Ti phase can be detected in the forged Cu-4.5wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite, meaning that titanium addition is reacted with copper to form Ti-Cu intermetallics during the hot forging. Thus, we can speculate that the flake-shaped piece in the Cu-3wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite is Ti-Cu intermetallics that are not detectable by XRD due to its amount is very small (Fig. 2c). These flake pieces can deteriorate the adhesion between TiC layer and diamond and cause the formed TiC layer spall from the diamond particles. Thus, the coverage of diamond by TiC interface is only slightly increased while increasing the titanium content from 1 wt% to 3wt% for the forged copper/diamond composite, and dramatically reduced for the forged Cu-4.5wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite due to large number of Cu₄Ti phase are formed to cause serious TiC spallation.

Fig. 5a shows the morphology of the extracted diamond particles from the forged Cu-1.5wt%-55vol.%Dia composite. It can be seen that the TiC interface layer is almost formed on the all diamond particles' surface, and the coverage of diamond by TiC is about 90%. TEM image (Fig.5b) shows that TiC layer is formed between the diamond (bright region) and the copper (dark region), which is confirmed by SAED. The thickness of TiC interface layer is about 80nm and it has a serrated shape. This may be caused by the preferential formation and growth of TiC on the diamond surface, and the detailed reasons will be reported in our further research. The measured thermal conductivity of the Cu-1.5wt%-55vol.%Dia composite is about 388W/m·K, and this value nearly twice that of AlN which is current best practice of the heat sink materials used in the high-power electronic devices.

Fig. 4 SEM images of the nitric-corroded Cu-3wt%Ti-65vol.%Dia composite forged at 1050°C

Fig.5 Morphology of the extracted diamond particles from the Cu-1.5wt%-55vol.% Dia composite: (a) and TEM microstructure of the composite's interface: (b)

4 CONCLUSION

The conclusion can be drawn as below:

(1) The combination of induction sintering and forging is a feasible and cost-effective way to fabricate copper/diamond composite from powder preform;

(2) TiC interface layer is formed between the copper and the diamond in the fabricated composite, but when titanium addition is over 3wt% in the copper alloy, the formed TiC interface will spall from the diamond surface due to the formation of Ti-Cu intermetallics;

(3) An effective interface layer is formed in the Cu-1.5wt%Ti-55vol%Dia composite, leading to the composite has a thermal conductivity of 388W/m·K, it almost double that of AlN which is current best practice of heat sink materials used for high-power electronic devices.

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